

LEARNING MANAGEMENT UTILIZING GOOGLE CLASSROOM LEARNING MEDIA TO IMPROVE DISTANCE LEARNING

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Abstract

The background to this research is the pandemic situation, which requires us to implement health protocols, namely maintaining distance/not gathering together, wearing masks and washing our hands frequently. All lines must implement health protocols, including in the world of education. In order to break the chain of spread of the epidemic, schools have been closed for face-to-face learning in class during the Covid-19 pandemic. Learning from home through distance learning based on Minister of Education and Culture Circular Number 4 of 2020 aims to provide a meaningful learning experience for students, without being burdened with demands to complete all curriculum achievements for grade promotion or graduation. However, it focuses on life skills education, including regarding the Covid-19 pandemic. The specific aim of this research is to identify the activities carried out by teachers in the stages of the online distance learning management process which include the stages of planning, organizing, implementing and supervising online distance learning using Google Classroom media. Theoretical Foundations of Distance Learning (PJJ) Online Learning Systems in accordance with the Republic of Indonesia Minister of Education and Culture Decree No. 719/P/2020 concerning the need to implement a special conditions curriculum with special learning patterns in order to achieve educational goals even in special conditions. George R. Terry (Manullang, 1988:16) said that: "management is achieving goals that are set first by using other people". This research method uses a qualitative descriptive method. Meanwhile, the conclusion of this research is that the research findings reveal that teacher activities at each stage of online distance learning management using Google Classroom media have had an important impact on learning during this pandemic, including: (1) learning is more organized and well administered by using Google Classroom media classroom, (2) not limited by space and time but quota friendly because it is free (3) students are directly involved in the learning process by using the internet, (4) learning materials are easy to use, (5) practice data literacy and technology literacy skills.

Keywords: Learning Management, Google Classroom, Distance Learning.

A. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is one country in the world that is also not free from the corona virus outbreak, since it was announced that two people tested positive for the corona virus. This incident is the first case of the corona virus in Indonesia. The two victims were mother and child. The child is suspected of contracting the corona virus from a Japanese friend. Then, he accidentally transmitted the corona virus to his mother and then they underwent treatment at the Sulianti Saroso Infectious Disease Hospital (RSPI), North Jakarta. President Joko Widodo and Minister of Health Terawan Agus Putranto made a direct announcement of the first corona case in Indonesia, namely on March 3 2020, then the President appealed to the public not to panic. However, responding to the massive news about Covid-19 has changed many things in people's lives.

The pandemic situation requires us to implement health protocols, namely maintaining distance/not gathering together, wearing masks and washing our hands frequently. All lines must implement health protocols, including in the world of education. In order to break the chain of spread of the epidemic, schools have been closed for face-to-face learning in class during the Covid-19 pandemic. This is done to avoid clusters of virus spread in schools. Reflecting on the experience of other countries such as South Korea, Singapore, Vietnam and Australia which temporarily opened schools and immediately closed them again due to virus transmission despite the implementation of strict health protocols.

As a result, according to Unesco data, more than 91% of the world's student population has been affected by school closures due to the Covid-19 pandemic. Likewise, students in Indonesia are affected by the temporary closure of schools from face-to-face activities. They are expected to be able to continue studying online using applications used by teachers or schools or offline depending on the status of where the students are, whether they are covered by internet networks, quota availability or cellphones.

By prioritizing the spirit of independent learning, distance learning is wide open. Without having to face-to-face in class, a teacher creates a virtual class with the help of existing technology. Online media is a strategic choice for running virtual classes. There are many media options available, for example Whatsapp group, zoom, webex, google meet, edmodo, teacher's room, google form, google classroom and others.

The question arises how can the national education system ensure that all learners have equal access to quality education during this unprecedented crisis? Therefore, the work from home (WFH) and Distance Learning programs or also known as Learning From Home have emerged.

Learning from home through distance learning based on the Minister of Education and Culture Circular Letter Number 4 of 2020 aims to provide a meaningful learning experience for students, without being burdened with demands to complete all curriculum achievements for the purposes of grade promotion and graduation. But focusing on life skills education, among others regarding the Covid-19 pandemic. Provide a variety of learning activities and learning tasks between students, according to their respective

interests and conditions, including considering the gap in access/learning facilities from home. As well as providing feedback on evidence or products of learning activities from home that are qualitative and useful for teachers, without being required to give a score.

The choice of media characteristics that suit the teaching materials is a very important thing to prepare at the beginning of designing distance learning. With learning changing from face-to-face to online in a short time without any prior preparation, suddenly teachers and schools are required to use online media according to their respective abilities and opportunities. So there are various learning media used by teachers and schools, the most important thing is that students can learn at home. Likewise, students without direct knowledge and skills are required to take part in online learning in accordance with their respective schools' online learning. So it is not surprising that in the field many new problems have emerged related to the change from face-to-face learning to online distance learning, both faced by schools, teachers and students. Initial observations made by researchers on teachers revealed that the selection of media and design of distance learning was carried out in a haphazard manner and the online learning media used was varied and many teachers used Google Classroom because they felt it was quite easy, practical and could represent online distance learning. This is the focus of researchers to study improving the quality of the distance learning process in material by utilizing Google Classroom media for teachers.

Smaldino et al. (2008) quoted by Sabran and Edi Sabara (2018) stated that: technology and media can play a big role in learning. If the teaching is teacher-centered, technology and media are used to support the presentation of the teaching. On the other hand, if teaching is student-centered, students are the main users of technology and media.

Nurfalah (2018) confirmed in the results of his research that optimizing Google Classroom features has an important impact on learning in the industrial revolution 4.0 era, including: (1) learning is carried out online using technology, (2) is not limited by space and time, (3) students are directly involved in the learning process that utilizes the internet, (4) learning materials are easy to access, (5) practice data literacy and technology literacy skills.

It is an interesting thing to be an academic study because there are many problems that can be researched and are very important in the present era where teachers and students are required to be technologically literate in distance learning. This research emphasizes the importance of teacher competence in designing learning, including choosing effective and efficient online media, preparing learning by starting with an analysis of current needs, choosing the right material, implementing learning and choosing the right evaluation tools to make the learning process successful in an effort to achieve competency. Proclaimed.

This research will highlight the importance of teacher competence as learning managers and students as learning subjects in utilizing the learning media that has been chosen, in this case Google Classroom media.

The above problem will be researched because it really interests researchers, the factors of designing, organizing, implementing and supervising online learning as a learning system are a special attraction for research as it is common knowledge that a researcher's interest is a factor that will greatly influence research results. A researcher who is serious about conducting research will have different results from a researcher who is half-hearted and even forced to carry out research.

B. THEORETICAL BASIS

In the 21st century, many things feel like there have been fundamental changes in various aspects of human life. The collapse of geographical barriers caused by globalization and advances in information technology has transformed the world into something like a giant village whose residents can easily interact, communicate and interact with each other whenever and wherever they are. The consequences resulting from changes in the environment and the world are extraordinary, demonstrated, among other things, through a number of phenomena as stated by Daryanto & Karim, Syaiful. (2016) stated that several examples of phenomena that we can experience include: 1) The flow of various physical and non-physical resources (data, information and knowledge) from one place to another freely and openly; 2) Increased collaboration and cooperation between nations in the process of creating highly competitive products and/or services, directly or indirectly, has shifted world economic power from “west” to “east”; 3) The flood of products and services from foreign countries being marketed domestically, apart from increasing the temperature of competition in the business world, also has a direct influence on people's mindset and behavior in carrying out their daily lives; and 4) The influx of foreign workers from labor to executive levels entering the national labor market has placed local human resources in quite a dilemma position in the eyes of industry as users.

Then Daryanto & Karim, Syaiful. (2016) states that a national education paradigm for the 21st century can be formulated as follows: 1) to face the 21st century which is increasingly demanding technology and science in global society, our education must be oriented towards mathematics and natural science accompanied by social science and humanity. with a reasonable balance; 2) Science education not only makes students knowledgeable, but also adopts a scientific attitude, namely critical, logical, analytical and creative, but also accompanied by the ability to adapt; 3) At every level of education it is necessary to instill a spirit of independence, because personal independence underlies national independence, independence in carrying out cooperation that respects and respects each other.

The aim of national education in the 21st century is to realize the ideals of the nation, namely an Indonesian nation that is prosperous, its people happy, with an honorable and equal position with other nations in the global world, through the formation of society as a quality human resource, namely independent individuals. , willing and capable to realize the ideals of their nation (BSNP, 2010). In line with the above, the Ministry of Education and Culture has formulated that the 21st century learning paradigm focuses on students'

ability to find out from various sources, then formulate problems, and think analytically and cooperate and collaborate in solving problems.

In the 21st century there are various main specialties as written by Daryanto & Karim, Syaiful. (2016). the first is the realization of a global society which is an agreement between nations, namely the opening of wider mobility between one country and another in various matters. The second is that this century will be dominated by the development of science and technology which is increasingly sophisticated and integrated with the social sciences and humanities. In order to be able to compete in this global society, but also have sufficient mastery over the social sciences and humanities and their development. In this century, each science no longer has to work alone, but various branches of science can work together, not only within science, technology or social science and humanities groups, but in many ways between several groups.

Although the development of advanced science and technology is for tertiary institutions, the readiness of students is largely determined by the results of pre-university education, starting from basic education to senior secondary education, even starting from early childhood education. Thus the series of each level of education, at least starting from basic education to tertiary education must be a chain, each of which consists of links with the characteristics of LPMP. From a variety of learning sources, formulate problems, think analytically and collaborate and collaborate to find solutions to existing problems.

Without us knowing it, the 21st century has been running for more than a decade in the world of education and we have felt a shift (Shifting = if you may borrow the term used by Renald Kasali) and even a principled and realistic one at the level of philosophy, direction and goals. This drastic change cannot be separated from the revolution that has occurred in the progress of computer science and technology, especially in the fields of cognitive science, bio-molecular, information technology and nano-science which have become icons/markers of the 21st century.

Globalization has become the most prominent icon of the 21st century which has caused the collapse of geographic and demographic barriers so that the world is like a world village whose inhabitants are interconnected by utilizing the advantages of information technology, so that they work together to become a unified society. In this group of people there are educational elements that must and should change with the changing times by utilizing information and communication technology in the world of education, which has led to narrowing and eliminating the "space and time" factor which has been an aspect that determines the speed and success of mastering knowledge. knowledge by mankind.

- a. Challenges in the world of education around the world. In order to be able to provide an understanding and deepening of phenomena in the 21st century, a desire to be open-hearted and open-minded is needed which is often quoted by education actors, that: "It seems that at this time the world of education aims to prepare the next generation 21st century, By educators born in the 20th century, as well as through educational/schooling institutions in the 19th century, by applying 18th-century learning methods (Anonymous). Is that quote true? This depends on the point of view

from which we see it. Therefore, the current task of education is to narrow the existing gap by trying to get out of the comfort zone a little bit, all elements of business education to make breakthroughs/innovations need to be tried and the use of technology needs to be utilized as much as possible by educational actors at all levels because our students are currently Those at the high school level and below are natives of the 21st century.”

- b. Education actually has a quite noble goal, namely to prepare students to live in their era, by equipping them with the skills, skills and competencies that will be needed in their era to the fullest extent possible. Competencies that are very necessary for them to enter the 21st century. Based on the 21st century global curriculum framework, according to BSNP (2010: 44) teachers can develop the following skills or competencies in an effort to prepare students to face global competition, including:
 - 1) Critical Thinking and Problem Solving: Responding to a future full of uncertainties and increasingly complex problems, students need to be given training to improve competence in providing reasonable reasoning, understanding and making creative solutions to increasingly complex problems. They are also challenged to understand the interconnections between existing systems, so that they are used to trying to solve the problems they face in the real world independently, so they are able to compile and reveal, analyze, and finally are able to make decisions and overcome the problems they face.
 - 2) Creativity and Innovation: In the school environment students are accustomed to honing their skills in developing, implementing and conveying new ideas to others, being open and responsive to new and different perspectives. Creating new innovations creatively and acceptable in the field, working creatively is the ending so they can survive in their era.
 - 3) Communication: In the 21st century the ability to understand, manage and create effective, polite and acceptable communication in various forms/content orally and in writing and by utilizing multimedia is an obligation that must be simulated in educational institutions in daily learning activities in order to prepare students contributed positively to its time. How they construct ideas so that they are clear and logical.
 - 4) Collaboration: Humans as social creatures really need other people to navigate their lives, regardless of their status. The keywords are collaboration, leadership, responsibility, prioritizing empathy, productivity and adaptability in various roles and respecting different perspectives. Students carry out personal roles and must also synergize with activities in groups in achieving standards and goals that are set together and understand ambiguity as a dynamic of life. Life Skills in the 21st Century must be instilled as early as possible in students, including:
 - a) Leadership. Students learn to realize an objective, honest and logical attitude.
 - b) Initiative. What can students do to overcome environmental problems.

- c) Flexibility. How students choose the right option based on the conditions of the situation at that time.
- d) Social Skills. How students respond to differences.
- e) Independent. Students must be able to manage their time so that assignments are completed on time

In the 21st century a person will survive if they have mastered 6 basic literacies, namely reading-writing literacy, numeracy literacy, scientific literacy, information and communication technology literacy, financial literacy, cultural literacy and citizenship plus three additional literacies, namely health literacy, road safety literacy., disaster mitigation), criminal literacy (for elementary school students it is called “safe school”). Generation Z children must be equipped with information, media and technology literacy that they will apply in their daily lives. The Minister of Education and Culture (2017) emphasizes the three literacy which are the basic capital in navigating life in the 21st century with the following understanding:

- a. Information Literacy: This includes the ability to access, evaluate and use information for the benefit of one's life. People who are literate in terms of information will enable them to color their lives and the environment around them. Who controls the information he will rule this world.
- b. Media Literacy: Media literacy is someone who is able to use process skills such as awareness, analysis, reflection and action to deal with natural messages contained in the media. Those who are literate in this matter will be wise in responding to media diversity. They can also access, analyze, evaluate and create messages in various forms of media, create an understanding of the role of mass media in society, and build important skills from information resulting from inquiry and self-expression including the ability to convey messages from themselves and to provide influence and information. to others. Why are the mass media different, the content of the news is different depending on the interests that the media has.
- c. Technological Literacy: How students convey knowledge more effectively through the use of digital communication technology High-level skills in considering information, media, and technology in the surrounding environment that this technological literacy demands. Students are expected to master technological literacy for the success of their lives in the 21st century. (Adapted from Trilling & Fadel, 2009).

In line with the goals and essence of current teaching, UNESCO has briefly emphasized the four pillars of education as 21st Century Skills for Generation Z as follows:

- a. Learning to Find Out: Learning is a process of finding out by acquiring knowledge through the use of existing media or tools. Media can be in the form of books, people, the internet, and other technologies.

- b. Learning to Do: Learning to do or work, this is inseparable from learning to know because actions cannot be separated from knowledge. Learning to produce work is an effort to always work on and practice skills for professionalism at work. In connection with learning in the classroom, learning to do this really requires skills training on how students can use knowledge of the concepts or principles of certain subjects in other subjects or in everyday life.
- c. Learning to Become a Person: Learning to become a fully developed and whole person, related to the increasingly complex demands of life so that a character is needed in oneself. Learning to become a fully and intact and optimally developed person who has compatibility and balance in his personality be it moral, intellectual, emotional, spiritual, or social, so that in learning educators have an obligation to develop their potential according to their talents and interests so that students can determine the choice is according to his wishes.
- d. Learning to Live Together: In living side by side it is very important that we are aware of the diversity of society, both in terms of background, ethnicity, race, religion or education. Likewise, in learning a student must realize that diversity is a wisdom, this is not to be differentiated, but to realize that this diversity is incorporated in a community environment. Therefore, mutual assistance and respect for one another is necessary in order to create a safe and orderly society, so that one can learn and live in peace and togetherness.

The Role of the Teacher in 21st Century Learning, Wartomo (2019) Teachers currently have tough challenges where teachers must prepare their students to survive in the 21st century by training them with 21st century skills while the teacher is in the 20th century with the support of 19th century facilities as well as with the 18th century learning methods, therefore it is ensured that teachers must reduce this gap by improving their quality by mastering various fields, being proficient in pedagogical matters including learning and teaching technology, understanding the psychology of learning, and having counseling skills, following developments regarding policies regarding the latest educational curriculum and issues, able to use new media and technology in learning, and continue to apply values to form good personality and character. Therefore educators still have an important role

C. RESEARCH APPROACHES AND METHODS

1. Research Approach

This research utilizes a qualitative approach with a descriptive developmental study design. Research directed at providing systematic and accurate explanations of symptoms, facts, or events regarding the characteristics of a particular population or area. This research approach utilizes a qualitative approach because it explores the problem very deeply.

According to S. Nasution (2003:18): "Qualitative research is also called naturalistic research. It is called qualitative because the nature of the data collected is qualitative, not

quantitative, because it does not use measuring instruments. It is called naturalistic because the research field situation is “natural” or natural, as it is, without being manipulated, regulated by experiments or tests. “This qualitative research is general theory, not hypothesis testing, so the resulting theory is in the form of substantive theory and theories based on grounded theory.”

According to Moleong (2005:6), qualitative research is research that intends to understand phenomena about what is experienced by research subjects, for example behavior, perceptions, motivations, actions, etc. holistically, and by means of descriptions in the form of words and language, on a special natural context and by utilizing various natural methods.

2. Research Object

The object of this research is teacher activities at the online distance learning management stage using Google Classroom media.

3. Data Collection Technique

In an effort to collect data, researchers take steps starting from preparation, organizing, implementing, evaluating and collecting data until the data is classified and constructed in a research report.

Data collection techniques are carried out through:

a. Observation

Participant observation according to Bodgan (Moleong, 2003:117) is: Research characterized by social interaction that takes quite a long time between the researcher and the subject in the object environment, during which data in the form of field notes is collected systematically and applies without interruption. Observation is also one of the most common data collection techniques in qualitative research methods. Observation is essentially an activity that utilizes the five senses, including sight, smell, hearing, to obtain the information needed to answer research problems. The results of observations are in the form of activities, events, events, objects, certain conditions or situations, and one's emotional feelings. Observations are made to obtain a real picture of something.

According to Bungin (Rahadjo, 2011: 5) suggests several forms of observation, namely:

- 1) Participatory observation is a data collection method used to collect research data through observation and sensing where the researcher is involved in the daily life of the informant.
- 2) Unstructured observations are observations made without utilizing observation guidelines, so that researchers develop their observations based on developments that occur in the field.
- 3) Group observation is an observation made by a group of research teams on an issue raised as the object of research.

The usefulness of data collection techniques in the form of participant observation is to collect data in the form of field notes and events in learning management activities using Google Classroom media. Researchers here take advantage of participatory observation in order to be directly involved in observations made at research sites online.

b. Interview

Interview according to Moleong (2003: 120) is: “a conversation with a specific purpose. This conversation was conducted by two parties, namely the interviewer (interviewer) and the interviewee. Interviews in qualitative research are usually of the unstructured type of interview. Meanwhile, unstructured interviews are interviews in which the interviewer determines the problem and questions to be asked. In the beginning, specific questions were not prepared, because it was not possible to predict the information that would be provided by the respondent, it was not clear in which direction the discussion would develop.”

There are several types of interviews that can be used, according to Sudarwan (2002), “based on the structure, in qualitative research there are two types of interviews namely; (1) relatively closed interviews, where questions were focused on specific and general topics and assisted by a fairly detailed interview guide; (2) open interviews, in which the researcher gives the respondent the freedom to speak broadly and in depth. In this research both were implemented.”

c. Document Review

Documentation studies according to M. Rahardjo (2011:6) that: Documentation studies where information can be obtained through facts stored in the form of letters, diaries, photo archives, meeting results, souvenirs, event dates and so on. Data in the form of documents like this can be used to dig up information that occurred in the past. Researchers need to have theoretical sensitivity to interpret all these documents so that they are not just meaningless items.

This method is used to obtain data in the form of management of teaching and learning activities by utilizing Google Classroom media during the pandemic which includes planning, organizing, implementing and monitoring which includes evaluation and supervision activities.

d. Literature Study

To study various written sources such as books, journals and magazines research results in order to open up theoretical research which in essence can enrich the analysis and discussion of research results whose results can be used for the presentation and interpretation of data as well as a theoretical review of the quality of the distance learning process by utilizing the media Google Classroom.

D. RESEARCH RESULT

Based on the data obtained in the field, the research results can be presented.

1. Learning Planning Stage

Teacher activities at the online Learning Planning Program stage using Google Classroom during the Covid-19 pandemic are as follows: Teachers in Subject Teacher Deliberation gather to address school policies in distance learning regarding what things need to be prepared. Starting from planning what media and materials to use, then together in the workshop making plans for online Subject Teacher Deliberation after evaluating what we had done in the first three months of Subject Teacher Deliberation when suddenly we had to learn online and at that time there was no preparation. The evaluation results are used as input for a better implementation of the next Subject Teacher Deliberation. As far as the teachers know, school funding to support the implementation of learning comes from central BOS funds, such as adding bandwidth, teacher quotas and RMP students receiving quota assistance.

Teachers are of the opinion that the important standards in national education standards during the pandemic are management standards, financing standards and facility standards so that online learning can be carried out well and what is no less important are staff/human resource standards who will be directly involved in implementing online distance learning. Teachers carry out assessments of Core Competencies (KI) - Basic Competencies (KD) which are in accordance with the emergency curriculum as well as the emergency curriculum syllabus. Considering the current conditions, the learning media is adapted to online distance learning, choosing the right online learning media, which is child friendly and not too complicated and quota friendly which does not require a large quota. Such as Google Classroom, PPT, YouTube regarding learning and preparation in the form of a syllabus in terms of making simple lesson plans, materials, media, methods, learning activities adapted for online learning which of course adapts to the emergency curriculum with simplified KD. The data above comes from the interview answers of the teachers. The characteristics of the media adjust to the material to be delivered by utilizing what is contained in Google Classroom. There are many things that can be used, the most important thing is that if you can do it, it won't be a burden on children who don't eat up too much quota, for example using applications that can include a link to Google Classroom which is "free".

2. Learning Organizing Stage

Teachers' activities at the stage of organizing online learning using Google Classroom during the Covid-19 pandemic as implementers in the field. The above information can be found in the interview data as follows: The selected content is essential, teachers must be wiser in this online distance learning, characteristics of students It must be considered, it is not allowed to force the conditions of students, they must really pay attention to this online learning. Teachers are trying to optimize all the features in Google Classroom so that the current online distance learning is better than the previous distance learning.

Teachers are required to be more creative in preparing this online distance learning so that students are not bored and learning is more interesting.

Not much different from face-to-face learning tools, such as syllabus, lesson plans, attendance books and grade books. Its characteristics are simpler, adapt to simplification of content, and of course suit online learning activities which are different from face-to-face. Also in learning objectives, the elements of ABCD (audience, behavior, conditioning, degree) are not exactly the same as face-to-face. For example, the behavior required is simpler, for example the conditioning is done online and the degree is not too high. What is important is that the students have followed the learning and it is good. Everything adapts to online learning.

Teachers use various sources such as from Education websites which are widely available on the internet. Its simple material characteristics are essential. Likewise, the characteristics of the media adapt to the material that will be delivered by utilizing what is available in Google Classroom. There are many things that can be used, the most important thing is that if possible it doesn't burden children who don't eat too much quota (quota-friendly) for example. Use applications that can be linked to Google Classroom data because they are free.

3. Implementation Stage

The activities of the teachers in the stages of implementing online learning using Google Classroom during the Covid-19 pandemic, the following information can be found in the interview data as follows: will do today. So apperception is carried out using the forum feature. The material provided in the core activities is delivered directly in Google Classroom, shared in the form of videos, links or ppt. The material is in accordance with the syllabus, for example material about health, or procedures for making or doing something using English, and when closing activities are attempted even though time often runs out, while for interaction between students and teachers you can use Google Meet or in Google Classroom you can through the forum feature and sometimes with the help of the WhatsApp group. So the initial, core and closing activities are conditioned by the time available.

Even though the interaction between students in Google Classroom is rather difficult, it is most conditioned when using the Google meet feature or when students answer and the teacher asks other students to respond. When using Google Meet it's easier to interact between students and teachers, or if Google Classroom can go through the forum feature.

At the time of implementation, initially the students' interest was good, but due to technical problems such as difficulty uploading, poor signal, sometimes students gave up wanting to go offline and the more they came here, the tendency was lazy, maybe they felt bored.

4. Evaluation and Supervision Stage

The activities of teachers at the controlling stage (Evaluation and Supervision) of online learning during the Covid-19 pandemic, the information below can be found in the interview data as follows: assessment, be it in writing, orally, as well as recorded data

and can be disclosed at any time. Apart from Google Classroom using other media such as Quizizz. Process assessment is usually carried out at every meeting to see student understanding, Daily Assessments are carried out after several meetings after one KD is completed, both knowledge and skills assessments. Attitude assessment Attitude assessment can be done during habituation activities, or while in the learning process or by looking at attendance, whether assignments are submitted on time, seeing student creativity, student activity, or when they answer our greetings in class.

The Supervision process is carried out by the Principal who can enter the application because the school account is used so it can be monitored directly who is teaching or not. Or the principal enters the classroom to directly observe the processes that occur, or when using the Google meet feature the principal can directly observe the processes that occur in learning.

E. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

1. Conclusion

The conclusions in this study are: a) planning; b) Organizing; c) Implementation; and d) Supervision.

There needs to be teacher patience in carrying out the management stages of the online learning system using Google Classroom media. Implementation of online learning using Google Classroom in an effort to organize productive schools during the pandemic. This research focuses on the activities of teachers in improving the quality of online distance learning by utilizing Google Classroom as a learning medium during distance learning by optimizing each stage of online distance learning management. The stages in the online distance learning management process used by teachers and school management are through the stages of planning, organizing, implementing and supervising in which there is an evaluation and supervision process using Google Classroom media.

Research findings reveal that teacher activities at each stage of online distance learning management using Google Classroom media have had an important impact on learning during this pandemic, including: (1) learning is more organized and well administered by using Google Classroom media, (2) not limited by space and time but quota friendly because it is free (3) students are directly involved in the learning process by using the internet, (4) learning materials are easy to use, (5) practice data literacy and technology literacy skills.

2. Implications

- a. Management of online distance learning by utilizing Google Classroom media through the stages of Planning, Organizing, Implementation, Supervision which is often abbreviated as POAC in a systematic manner.
- b. The first stage in the management of online distance learning is that planning starts with reviewing and deciding on policies to be taken and then continuing to analyze the needs of human resources, infrastructure and funding as well as curriculum

analysis, emergencies for compiling syllabuses, lesson plans according to essential material, sharing competency capabilities the teachers.

- c. The organizing stage includes activities to strengthen human resources, both educators and education staff, by holding workshops or training that are appropriate based on needs and on target, for example, dividing teaching assignments, making distance learning schedules.
- d. The Implementation Stage by optimizing distance learning using google classroom media was initially supported and assisted by the whats up group (WAG) and then supported by other media/applications such as google forms, you tube, Edmodo and modules so that learning is more effective and efficient .
- e. The Supervision Stage in which there is a process of evaluating student competence and supervision of the implementation of the online distance learning process in order to reflect on performance as well as at the same time as input material for future distance learning to make it even better.

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